

Photo-physical Study of Al doped ZnO thin films grown by sol-gel method

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Abstract

In the present study ZnO:Al Thin films were prepared by sol-gel method. We have fabricated the aluminium doped ZnO thin films by varying the deposition cycle and annealing temperature. The spin-coating speed of the samples were 3000 rpm for 30 sec and subjected to 300 °C and 500 °C annealing temperatures to obtain uniform films. The obtained films were characterized by using X-ray diffraction to determine the crystalline structure of the prepared films. The surface morphology study was carried out by high resolution field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM). Optical properties of AZO. The XRD pattern of AZO thin films revealed the hexagonal crystal structure. The surface morphology of AZO thin films was uniform and nanocrystalline particle growth was observed. AZO thin films were highly transparent (>90 %) in the visible region

Keywords: Thin Films, AZO, solar cell, Sensor XRD, FE-SEM.

1. Introduction

ZnO is well-known functional n-type metal oxide semiconductors of the II-VI group. These materials have drawn significant attention because of their favorable physical and chemical properties such as wide band gap, good transparency, low processing cost, excellent gas sensing ability, good stability in ambient atmosphere and non-toxicity [1-2]. The functionalities of these compound semiconductors can be improved by doping the appropriate metals into the host materials and it plays a vital role in solar cell technology. The gas sensing property is the surface phenomenon, in which interaction of analyte gas molecules with the adsorbed oxygen alters the sheet resistance of the material [3-4]. Therefore, it is very important to select an appropriate dopant for a particular gas sensing application to improve its sensing performance and selectivity to a single gas [5].

Undoped and doped ZnO and SnO₂ thin films have been widely used as a gas sensor for the different gases [6]. Generally for the high performance gas applications, ZnO thin films preferably doped with Al, Ga, or In are used.

There are different ways to prepare the thin films of ZnO:Al, metal organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD), Chemical vapor deposition (CVD), DC or RF Sputtering, hydrothermal method, facial spray pyrolysis technique, pulsed laser deposition and sol-gel [7-14]. Among these techniques, sol-gel method offers some particular advantages because it has the ability to produce a solid state material from a chemically homogenous precursor. In sol-gel method, atomic level mixing of reagents is able to produce the complex inorganic materials such as ternary and quaternary oxides at lower processing temperature and shorter synthesis time. Furthermore, by using sol-gel technique, it is possible to achieve greater control over the growth of particle size and surface morphology of the thin films.

Therefore, in the present investigation, for all three different kinds of thin films sol-gel method was employed. The Al doped ZnO thin films were prepared with different Al doping concentration for humidity sensor. The effects of doping concentration and annealing temperatures on the structures, morphology of thins films were studied via X-ray diffraction, filed effect scanning electron microscopy techniques, respectively. Finally, sensing properties of all three thin films were measured.

2. Experimental Details

The chemicals used in all three different experiments were purchased from commercial sources and used without further purification. For the preparation of ZnO:Al thin films only alumina substrates were used. The glass and alumina substrates were cleaned with soap solution, acetone and ethanol via ultra-sonication process for 15 min at each stage. Finally, the substrates were dried at 110 °C for 10 min prior to spin coating.

2.1. Al doped ZnO (AZO) thin film preparation

Al doped ZnO thin films were deposited on soda-lime glass and alumina substrates by sol-gel method. For the preparation of AZO thin films, zinc acetate dihydrate and aluminum nitrate nonahydrate were used as source materials for zinc and aluminum. 0.55 M zinc acetate solution was prepared in absolute ethanol and desire amount of aluminum nitrate was added to zinc precursor solution. The complexing agent was added to obtain the clear solution. The AZO precursor solution was spin coated on the glass or alumina substrates at 3000 rpm for 30 sec and samples were dried at 300 °C for 10 min. This process was repeated to number of times in order to obtain the required thickness of the AZO thin films. Finally the films were sintered at different annealing temperatures such as 550 °C.

2.4. Characterization Techniques

The formed phases in the prepared thin films were identified via X-ray diffraction. Field-effect scanning electron microscope is used to study surface morphology of the samples. The UV-VIS spectrophotometer was used to study the optical properties of the AZO.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Al doped ZnO (AZO) Thin Films

3.1.1 Structural Study

Figure 1 shows the X-ray diffraction pattern of glass/ZnO:Al thin films annealed at 500 °C for 30 min. The Al doping concentration was 0.6 at% with respect to zinc. The XRD pattern shows the (101) peak orientation at 36.207 degree, confirming the hexagonal structure of ZnO thin film (JCPDS: 80-0074). The intensity of (101) peak increased with increasing in thickness of Al:ZnO films. The obtained results are in consistence with the previously reported data [1,8].

The poor crystallinity of AZO thin films can be attributed to the excess amount of aluminum present in the AZO film. Therefore, to improve the crystallinity of the Al doped ZnO thin film; the AZO thin films were prepared on alumina instead of soda-lime glass substrates so that annealing temperature can be increased beyond the 500 °C.

Figure 1: X-ray diffraction pattern of Al:ZnO thin films annealed at 500°C

3.1.2 Surface morphology study

Figure 2 shows the top view SEM images of AZO thin films. From the top view images it is observed that for 2 layers of spin coating compact film is obtained. It is found that 10-20 nm size AZO nanoparticles were obtained, as shown in figure 1. It also shows that the double layer spin coating of Al doped thin films provide a homogenous and pinhole free thin films.

Figure 2: FE-SEM image of Al:ZnO thin films deposited on glass substrates

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The small crystalline size of Al:ZnO thin films confirms the nanocrystalline growth of Al:ZnO thin films.

To study the optical properties, UV-Vis spectrum of Al:ZnO thin films was measured. Figure 3 shows the transmittance spectra of Aluminium doped ZnO thin films. It is noticed that the obtained thin films are 95 % transparent in the visible of solar radiation spectrum, which is excellent for the optoelectronic device applications particularly third generation solar cells and organic light-emitting diode.

Fig.3: Plot of optical transmittance versus wavelength for AZO films deposited on soda lime glass substrates.

Conclusions

Al doped ZnO (AZO) thin films were successfully deposited via sol-gel method. The XRD study of AZO films annealed at 500 °C revealed the hexagonal structure of ZnO thin film. The broad orientation of (100) peak confirms nanocrystalline nature of the grown films. Uniform and smooth surface morphology was noticed from SEM analysis.

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